

A Deep Regression Framework towards Laboratory Accuracy in the Shop Floor of Microelectronics

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Abstract—Deep Learning (DL) has certainly improved industrial inspection while significant progress has been also achieved in metrology with impressive results reached through their combination. However, it is not easy to deploy metrology sensors in a factory, as they are expensive, and require special acquisition conditions. In this paper, we propose a methodology to replace a high-end sensor with a low-cost one introducing a data-driven Soft Sensor (SS) model. Concretely, a residual architecture (R^2 esNet) is proposed for quality inspection, along with an error-correction scheme to lessen noise impact. Our method is validated in PCB manufacturing, through the identification of defects related to glue dispensing before the attachment of silicon dies. Finally, a detection system is developed to localize PCB regions of interest, thus offering flexibility during data acquisition. Our methodology is evaluated under operational conditions achieving promising results, whereas PCB inspection takes a fraction of the time needed by other methods.

Index Terms—Defect detection, PCB, ResNet, smart manufacturing

I. INTRODUCTION

INDUSTRY 4.0 aims to automate manufacturing processes using smart technologies and has greatly benefited from recent advancements in Deep Learning (DL). The success of DL has been demonstrated by its numerous applications in a variety of different industrial sectors ranging from telecommunications [1] to electronics [2]. However, the large amounts of accurately annotated data needed to train DL models necessitate the deployment of multiple high-accuracy sensors for industrial process monitoring. The use of high-end laboratory sensors, which are accurate, stable, and robust, is not always a feasible solution due to the high deployment and maintenance cost they incur. Hence it is necessary to rely on less accurate, yet low-cost sensors.

This paper is a direct extension of a previous work by Dimitriou et al. [3], in which a Printed Circuit Board (PCB) defect detection system is developed. Prior to the attachment of integrated circuits, it is necessary to dispense conductive glue

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on the PCB's substrate surface, during which defects related to the dispensed glue volume may occur. Identification of such defects is achieved through the use of a modular scanning system and a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (3DCNN), which regresses the volume of each glue deposit of a PCB. Interestingly, glue volume is accurately estimated even after die attachment when only part of the glue is visible and partial information about its shape is available.

Despite the promising results obtained, this method relies on the use of a laser profilometer which is expensive, slow, needs to be calibrated, and requires controlled illumination conditions during measurements. These limitations are the main motivation for our work, where we propose to replace the laser profilometer with a single RGB camera and a deep learning architecture that provides laboratory level accuracy in the shop floor (in situ). The replacement of a profilometer with an industrial camera has numerous advantages, as it significantly reduces the cost of automated inspection, making it a suitable choice for in-situ deployment, whereas both data acquisition and processing are faster, thus notably reducing inspection time. To automate the inspection process using a low-cost sensor, ground truth is acquired in the laboratory by analytically calculating the volume of each sample from its corresponding 3D point cloud representation and is subsequently used to train a deep network that estimates glue volume from 2D image data. Additionally, we develop a segmentation and detection system that localizes glue regions within the image irrespective of the PCB's orientation. Finally, we propose a method to deal with label noise, inherently existent due to the finite resolution of the 3D scans, using only a few reliable measurements. The main novelties of our work are summarized below:

- We propose a new methodology to replace expensive sensors with in situ ones
- We provide increased flexibility during data acquisition, as accurate part placement is not necessary
- We extrapolate a 3D variable (volume) from 2D data (RGB image)
- A modified Residual Network for Regression (R^2 esNet) is introduced, and the impact of different choices of depth is examined
- We demonstrate the potential of this approach in a semiconductor manufacturing use case
- A new benchmark dataset is generated.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the related work in soft sensors and metrology meth-

ods for defect detection for industrial applications. Section III outlines the examined defect detection use case as well as the proposed methodology. A detailed description of the available data is given and the various deep architectures used are introduced. In section IV, our methodology is evaluated and the experimental results are presented. Finally, Section V concludes this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we give an overview of the most recent work related to our method. Since we develop a Soft Sensor (SS) model to indirectly estimate glue volume from RGB image data and use the estimated value to identify defects, we further elaborate on the recent advancements in the fields of defect detection via deep learning, soft sensor models and AI.

A. Defect Detection via DL

The successful application of DL in the industry can be partially attributed to the introduction of several deep convolutional architectures that have revolutionized image classification and have since been used as backbone networks for various tasks. In [4], the authors introduce VGG, a deep convolutional architecture that makes use of multiple layers while keeping a small, fixed, 3×3 size for the convolutional kernels, which has since become a standard process. Proposing the use of residual connections, the authors in [5] develop ResNet, achieving state-of-the-art results in multiple image classification datasets. Extending this idea, DenseNet is proposed in [6], by concatenating the feature maps of each layer with the input of every subsequent layer, thus facilitating the gradient flow to the initial layers during backpropagation. To address the increasing demand for mobile and real-time embedded vision applications, the authors in [7] and [8] propose MobileNet, which is based on depthwise separable convolutions to lower the computational cost both during training and inference without significantly affecting performance.

In recent years, DL approaches have been successfully adopted for various industrial applications, mainly focusing on optimizing the production process through the identification of defective parts. In [3], upon which our work is based, the authors consider a PCB defect detection use case and develop a 3DCNN regression architecture called RNet to estimate the volume of a conductive glue deposit before die attachment. In [9], a data-driven fault diagnosis system is developed using a 2DCNN in combination with a parameter-free conversion method to transform 1D signals into 2D images, and its effectiveness is demonstrated on three distinct fault diagnosis use cases. Moreover, in [10] a deep convolutional transfer learning network is developed to address the discrepancy between source and target domain during training and testing and is evaluated on three motor bearing fault diagnosis datasets. The authors in [11] propose the use of a Fault Diagnosis Classification Convolutional Neural Network (FDC-CNN), which enables the association of the output of the first convolutional layer with the structural meaning of the raw data, making it possible to extract information regarding the cause of defects, and test their method on a chemical

vapor dataset. To cope with noisy data, a wavelet-inspired soft thresholding approach is adopted in [12] in which the optimal threshold values are learned, and it is applied for the identification of bearing and gear faults in rotating machines. A joint detection and classification scheme is proposed in [13] for steel plate defect inspection through the fusion of multilevel features. Another defect detection application in the hard metal industry is developed in [14], where data gathered from multiple sensors are used for quality assessment. In [15] the authors develop another feature fusion method exploiting Sparse Auto Encoders (SAE) whereas in [16], the use of a segmentation-based deep architecture that can generalize based on only few training samples is suggested to identify surface crack defects. Finally both [17] and [18] take advantage of deep learning models to identify welding defects.

B. Soft sensors & AI

Another line of DL applications in the industry, involves the development of Soft Sensors (SS) for the indirect monitoring of hidden variables during production. A data driven approach to estimate hazardous gas concentrations using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to decorrelate the input signals along with a Deep Belief Network (DBN) is proposed in [19]. Furthermore, a soft sensor application is developed in [20], where Support Vector Machines (SVM) and other predictive models are used to regress key variables in a refinery isomerization process. In a related application [21], a stacked auto encoder soft sensing model is introduced, where a product concentration prediction use case on an industrial debutanizer column process is examined. In [22], a nonlinear finite impulse response model is used to estimate the deflection of a polymeric mechanical actuator, whereas in [23] a semi-supervised approach is introduced to exploit unlabeled data. Another semi-supervised method is suggested in [24] to estimate the CO₂ concentration in an ammonia synthesis process. A spatiotemporal attention-based long short-term memory network is proposed in [26] and is evaluated on an industrial hydrocracking process use case.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section the proposed methodology is outlined. First, an overview of our method is given and the studied use case is described in detail. Next, the in situ sensing module under consideration is introduced along with the high-end sensor that is replaced. Finally, our R²esNet architecture and the segmentation model for glue detection are described.

A. Overview

In order to transfer the accuracy and robustness of a laboratory sensor in the shop floor we adopt the following approach: For each data sample, we obtain two distinct representations x^l and x^s , corresponding to the measurements acquired using a high-end laboratory sensor and a low-cost in situ one respectively. Subsequently, measurements x^l are used to create annotated samples by analytically estimating the quality variable under consideration through $y = f(x^l)$,

where $f(\cdot)$ is considered to be known. Exploiting the existing correspondence between the samples we create a dataset $\{(x_i^s, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ which is then used to train a deep network $h(x^s, \theta)$ such that:

$$h(x^s, \theta^*) \approx f(x^l) \quad (1)$$

where θ^* are the optimal network parameters estimated by minimizing the empirical cost as shown in (2)

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N L(h(x_i^s, \theta), y_i) \quad (2)$$

and $L(h(x_i^s, \theta), y_i)$ is any valid cost function. A schematic overview of this approach is given in Fig. 1. The deep network predicts the value $h(x^s, \theta) = \hat{y}$, and its parameters are tuned to minimize the prediction error $e = y - \hat{y}$.

Fig. 1: Schematic overview of the proposed methodology. During training a high-end sensor is used to extract ground truth measurements. Subsequently the low cost sensor along with the trained model are deployed in the shop floor.

B. Studied use case

The growing wave of small electronics products such as wearables and IoT devices has led to increased demand for small-scale printed circuit boards. A critical stage in the microelectronics manufacturing industry is the dispensing of conductive glue on an LCP substrate surface placed by a glue dispensing machine before the attachment of Integrated Circuits (ICs).

The volume of the dispensed glue deposit is a crucial variable that needs to be monitored during production as it directly affects the quality of the produced circuit. Specifically, excessive glue may lead to internal short circuits, whereas insufficient glue leads to weak die bonding. The current practice for the detection of such faulty conditions is the manual inspection of the PCB, which is both a time-consuming and highly inaccurate process.

The development of a soft sensor model for the monitoring of the dispensed glue volume and the inspection of a part benefits production and is considered crucial towards the automation of quality control. The use of a laboratory sensor such as a laser profilometer [3], even though produces highly accurate and reliable measurements, is expensive and may slow down production. Our proposed methodology aims to transfer the accuracy of a high-end sensor on the shop floor while simultaneously offering increased flexibility during the acquisition of measurements and highly reducing inspection time and cost. An example of a PCB consisting of 18 identical circuit modules is shown in Fig. 2. Each module contains several glue deposits whose volume needs to be monitored during inspection. There are five different types of glue containers as can be seen in Fig. 3, which we label A, B, C, D and E.

Fig. 2: Example of printed circuit board used for the development of the proposed system. Each PCB consists of two rows and contains 18 circuit modules in total.

Fig. 3: Examples of three circuit modules, each corresponding to a different state. The glue dispensed on circuit (a) is insufficient, on circuit (b) normal whereas on circuit (c) it is excessive.

C. Sensing module

For PCB inspection, the sensing modules under consideration include a modular laser scanning system (high-end sensor) and an industrial RGB camera (low-end sensor). The high-end setting comprises an Optimet Conopoint-10 sensor, a Newport XPS-RL2 motion controller, two linear stages, and the support breadboards. The same zig-zag scanning strategy as in [3] has been employed to reduce inspection time. Each glue deposit is scanned twice, once with a resolution of $50 \mu m$ and once with $20 \mu m$. Indicative point cloud representations of the acquired scans can be seen in Fig. 4, from where it is evident that the 3D geometric structure of the glues is successfully captured. The low-cost setup consists of a Baumer VCXG-201C.R industrial camera and a Fujinon machine vision CF25ZA-1S lens. The lens' focal length is $25 mm$ and thus, when placed in the right height, the PCB captures a large part of the image compared to the background, thus fully exploiting the setup's potential. All inference computations are performed using a Jetson AGX Xavier, and thus the whole system can easily be deployed in the shop floor following the edge computing paradigm. The proposed setup is shown in Fig. 5.

D. Generating a Dataset

Obtaining an annotated dataset requires expert knowledge and is usually a challenging and time-consuming process, especially in industrial applications where the sample parts, particularly defective ones, are scarce. Automating the annotation process is highly beneficial as it largely reduces the time and workload needed. To address this common issue, we propose two different glue volume estimation processes, one using the $50 \mu m$ to automatically generate a noisy dataset for

Fig. 4: 3D scans of glue types A,B,C,D, and E taken with a resolution of $20 \mu m$.

Fig. 5: Proposed setup consisting of a Jetson AGX Xavier and a machine vision camera.

training, and another using the $20 \mu m$ to manually generate a reliable and accurate set of measurements for validation purposes.

In both cases, for each regional scan RANSAC [25] is applied to estimate the substrate LCP surface plane. Subsequently, for the low resolution scans the points belonging to the glue deposits are identified as the outliers of the plane's model, whereas for the high resolution scans they are manually cropped. Each 3D point of the glue point cloud is then projected onto the estimated substrate plane to form a closed surface. Following this process, the resulting 3D representation is $x^l = G \cup S$, where $G = \{g_i\}_{i=1}^M$ is the glue cloud and $S = \{g'_i\}_{i=1}^M$ the corresponding projected substrate surface cloud. Glue volume is approximated using the formula:

$$V(x^l) = \sum_{i=1}^M \|g_i - g'_i\|_2 \Delta s_i \quad (3)$$

where Δs_i is the rectangular surface area element and $\|\cdot\|_2$ the standard Euclidean 2-norm of a vector. Δs_i depends on the resolution r of the point cloud through the relation $\Delta s_i = r^2$. Equation (3) is geometrically interpreted in Fig. 6. Essentially, the above formula is a discrete approximation of its continuous counterpart

$$V = \iint_D g(x, y) dx dy \quad (4)$$

where D is the domain of integration, and $g(x, y)$ the height of the glue deposit at any point. The coordinate system chosen is such that the substrate surface plane corresponds to $z = 0$.

Due to the existence of sensor noise during scanning, the imperfect plane fitting and glue-substrate segmentation of the point cloud, and the discretization error introduced in (3), the estimated glue volume is unavoidably corrupted by noise. Let v_i be the true volume value for sample i . By construction, we obtain a set of measurements $\{y_i^d\}_{i=1}^N$, estimated from the $20 \mu m$ resolution point clouds and a corresponding set

Fig. 6: Illustration of the analytical volume estimation process. Every point $g_i \in G$ is projected onto the substrate plane p , and the elementary volume Δv_i is calculated. The sum of all Δv_i approximates the total glue volume.

$\{y_i^s\}_{i=1}^N$, estimated from the $50 \mu m$ glue clouds. Both sets of measurements are corrupted by noise such that:

$$y_i^d = v_i + n_i^d \quad (5)$$

$$y_i^s = v_i + n_i^s \quad (6)$$

where $n_i^s \sim WN(\mu_i^s, \sigma^s)$ and $n_i^d \sim WN(\mu_i^d, \sigma^d)$ are modeled as white noise random processes, where it is assumed that $\sigma^d \ll \sigma^s$ and that $\mu_i^d \approx 0$. After acquiring the PCB images, all glue regions are manually cropped thus obtaining representations x_i^s , which are used to form a noisy training set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{Train}} = \{(x_i^s, y_i^s)\}_{i=1}^N$ and a testing set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{Test}} = \{(x_i^s, y_i^d)\}_{i=1}^M$ using the more reliable, dense resolution measurements for evaluation purposes.

E. Deep architectures

The developed system consists of a two step process. First, the acquired image is fed into an instance segmentation network that predicts the pixel coordinates of each glue deposit and classifies its type. Subsequently, each detected glue deposit is fed into a regression network that estimates its volume.

Segmentation & Detection: During the last few years, computer vision has immensely advanced, especially regarding object detection and instance segmentation tasks. Extensive research in the field has led to the development of two-stage detection methods, like the seminal Faster-RCNN [27] method that is capable of fast and accurate object detection through the utilization of a Region Proposal Network (RPN). A variant of Faster R-CNN, called Mask R-CNN, is introduced in [28] to perform semantic segmentation on the detected objects.

Since it is necessary to identify all glue deposits within an image, we use Mask R-CNN to first segment the PCB into its constituent modules and Faster R-CNN to detect and classify the glue deposits within each module. For each PCB, the coordinates of its modules are manually annotated. Five

of the PCBs are kept for training and one for testing. Due to the small-scale dataset available, we perform heavy data augmentation by applying random rotations, crops, random scaling, and random horizontal and vertical flips during training. Besides increasing the size of the dataset, augmentation also contributes to the development of the desired invariances. Subsequently, for every detected module, we fit the minimum area rectangle to its binary mask and warp the image using the rectangle's four corners. The glue detection Faster R-CNN is trained to localize all glue deposits within a module and classify their type. To this end, the pixel coordinates of all glue deposits are manually annotated to create a dataset. The same kind of augmentation is used as before to develop translational, rotational and scaling invariance. Both networks use a ResNet50 backbone and are pretrained on the ImageNet dataset [29]. Finally, by performing another affine coordinate transform using the detected bounding boxes, the glue deposit images are isolated. A schematic representation of the instance segmentation system is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Schematic representation of the proposed segmentation and detection system. The raw PCB image is fed into the segmentation network, and subsequently the extracted modules are fed into the detection network which regresses a bounding box for each glue deposit.

Volume Regression: To automate the glue volume estimation process, we develop R²esNet, a deep regression network based on the well-known Residual Network (ResNet) architecture [5]. Residual networks exploit the use of shortcut connections between intermediate layers, and by doing so can define very deep architectures that avoid overfitting and increase the convergence rate during training. As the authors advocate, it is easier to learn residual rather than direct mappings. The final layers of the network consist of a global average pooling layer, along with a 1000-way fully connected layer with softmax for classification.

To perform regression, we modify the existing ResNet architecture by replacing the last classification layer with a single-output fully-connected layer and omit the use of the softmax activation function. We experiment with three choices of depth by stacking 4, 8, and 16 residual blocks, which correspond to 10, 18, and 34 layers respectively. Each network is trained for 90 epochs using Adam with an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} , which is divided by 10 every 30 epochs. Weights are initialized as in [30] and trained from scratch.

All training samples are normalized by subtracting the per-channel mean and dividing by the standard deviation over the whole dataset, whereas the labels are scaled to the interval 0-1. Data augmentation is applied in the form of random rotations, translations, horizontal and vertical flips, as well as brightness, contrast, saturation, and hue jitter. Moreover, due to the small dataset available, we use a mini-batch size of one and therefore replace all batch normalization layers with layer normalization. The cost function used is the typical for regression MSE loss. The schematic overview of the proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 10.

Compared to other deep architectures, R²esNet achieves faster inference due to its reduced size, while the use of residual connections lowers the risk of overfitting. As in most industrial applications, annotated data is scarce, and computational resources are limited, we conclude that R²esNet is well suited for edge deployment. In general, the few hundred samples available would be inadequate to train a deep network and would likely result to the model overfitting the training data. However, due to the controlled image acquisition environment and the relatively small variability of the glue samples, even a small dataset is enough to successfully capture the problem's statistics.

Fig. 8: Plot of y_i^s and y_i^c on the left figure, and their difference $y_i^c - y_i^s$ on the right for type A glues. For better illustration purposes measurements y_i^c are sorted in ascending order.

Error Correction: As has been described in Subsection III-D, the available measurements for training are corrupted by white noise, and thus it is necessary to employ some regularization strategy to cope with this issue and develop robustness for the trained model. The two sets of measurements for type A glues are illustrated in Fig. 8. It is made evident that besides the random fluctuations present in the sparse resolution measurements, there also exists a deterministic bias directly correlated with the amount of the dispensed glue. The existence of this bias is attributed to the overestimation of the substrate plane's height, as well as the inability of RANSAC to correctly classify the points near the boundaries of the glue. Inspired by this observation, we hypothesize that the existent error is related to several other characteristics, such as glue shape, and can thus be partially predicted from the 2D input images. Formally, we assume that there exists a deterministic error term e_i^s such that:

$$y_i^s = v_i + e_i^s + n_i^s \quad (7)$$

In order to refine the network's predictions, we employ a parallel "error-correction" network that functions as a regularizer and whose aim is to regress the deterministic error from the input image x_i . The structure of the proposed model is illustrated in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Schematic representation of the proposed noise compensation methodology.

To minimize the computational load added through the error-correction network, we choose to employ a R²esNet architecture of depth 10 in every case. A small number of reliable dense resolution measurements acquired from the 20 μm scans is used for training, during which the parameters of the volume prediction network remain frozen. The same optimization and augmentation strategy is used as before. The small number of available training samples further justifies the choice of a shallower architecture.

Algorithm 1 Printed Circuit Board Inspection

Input: Raw RGB image $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times H \times W}$
Output: Estimated glue volumes $\mathcal{V} = \{v_{ij}\}_{i=1,j=1}^{K,M}$
 K : Number of Modules
 M : Number of glue deposits per module

- 1: PCB Segmentation $(m_i)_{i=1}^K \triangleright m_i$: Circuit module i
- 2: **for** $i = 1 : K$ **do**
- 3: Glue Localization $(g_{ij})_{j=1}^M \triangleright g_{ij}$ Glue deposit j
- 4: **for** $j = 1 : M$ **do**
- 5: Volume Estimation $v_{ij} = \text{R}^2\text{esNet}(g_{ij})$
- 6: **end for**
- 7: **end for**

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In this section, our proposed methodology is evaluated. First, our instance segmentation system is visually evaluated,

Fig. 10: Schematic overview of the proposed R²esNet10 architecture. The model consists of four residual blocks, an output and an input block. Each block sequentially performs convolution, layer normalization, rectification, convolution and layer normalization.

and its robustness to translations and rotations of the input image is demonstrated. Subsequently, we evaluate the developed regression model R²esNet. The three different choices of depth are compared through the use of 10-fold cross-validation, whereas testing set predictions are shown. Finally, inspection times for the six defective and non-defective parts are calculated and presented.

A. Module segmentation and glue detection

To evaluate the robustness of our segmentation model, we artificially apply random rotations and translations to the acquired input images to simulate the effect of part misplacement. As can be seen in Fig. 11, the developed system successfully segments the PCB into its modules in all three cases. Even in the more challenging cases, where the image is either rotated or translated, all modules are detected despite the partial occlusion near the boundaries of the PCB, which indicates that the system has learned to generalize. Qualitative results of our glue detection system are shown in Fig. 12. Notice that despite the large difference in both illumination and the amount of the dispensed glue deposits, all regions are accurately localized and their type is correctly predicted.

Fig. 11: Testing PCB segmentation results. In the first row the original image is segmented, in the second the image is translated before segmentation whereas in the third it is rotated.

B. Glue volume estimation

The available data for the development of the proposed system consists of 6 PCBs, each containing 18 circuit modules as shown in Fig. 2. There are 5 different types of glue containers annotated A, B, C, D and E, each corresponding to a different shape and amount of glue that needs to be placed on the LCP substrate surface as is illustrated in Fig 3. Within each circuit module, there are four placeholders for each glue type thus resulting in a total number of 20 placeholders per module. On the top row of one of the PCBs dies have been attached, and hence the total number of available samples per glue type is $5 \times 4 \times 18 + 4 \times 9 = 396$.

To obtain reliable testing results we adopt the following strategy to split the dataset into training, validation, and testing

Fig. 12: Examples of the detected glue regions within two PCB circuit modules.

sets: We keep the glues located in the third row of every module for testing, whereas the remaining samples are randomly divided into training and validation samples. This results in a 75%-25% training\validation-testing split, in which the testing set contains glues from all PCBs, and whose volume varies from very little to excessive, that way successfully capturing the whole dataset's statistics. For the same reasons, we use the ground truth volumes estimated using the $20\ \mu m$ resolution scans from the first row of each PCB to obtain a clean dataset, which is used to train the error-correction network. That way, the number of the resulting reliable training samples is 99. The average validation error over all 10 folds is shown in Fig. 13. We observe that the deepest model trained consisting of 34 layers performs the worst, whereas $R^2esNet10$ and $R^2esNet18$ perform comparably with $R^2esNet10$ converging faster in most cases.

In order to quantitatively evaluate and compare the developed models we use the Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) metric as shown in (8).

$$NRMSE = 100 \times \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^M (\hat{y}_i - y_i^d)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^M (y_i^d)^2}} \quad (8)$$

To evaluate the effectiveness of R^2esNet compared to other popular backbone architectures we perform the same experiments using VGG, DenseNet and MobileNetV2. For training, all hyperparameters are kept the same as in R^2esNet , whereas batch normalization layers are replaced with layer normalization. As in R^2esNet , we decrease the number of layers used by stacking 8 densely connected blocks for DenseNet, which results to a 20-layer network. Due to its efficient and lightweight implementation MobileNetV2 is kept intact, whereas a VGG network consisting of 11 layers is used. The average validation NRMSE and testing NRMSE are reported in Tables I and II respectively. Contrary to the usual case, where deeper architectures yield improved results, we observe the opposite, even though Residual Networks are known to tackle the degradation problem associated with increased depth. During cross-validation, in most cases $R^2esNet10$ produces the best results, whereas $R^2esNet34$ performs worse by a significant margin. In the testing set, irrespective of the choice of depth,

all networks perform approximately the same, whereas we observe a significant improvement when using a parallel error-correction network. Compared to other backbone architectures, R^2esNet performs better by a small margin in most cases, whereas the classical convolutional VGG network performs significantly worse.

TABLE I: Average Validation $NRMSE \times 100\%$, $50\ \mu m$.

Type	A	B	C	D	E
$R^2esNet10$	19.16	34.85	26.27	56.69	29.9
$R^2esNet18$	19.57	36.97	30.94	51.72	27.98
$R^2esNet34$	30.07	51.95	44.75	43.15	52.51
DenseNet	18.98	42.75	34.11	52.38	28.26
MobileNetV2	20.19	44.93	31.29	55.26	33.54
VGG	48.31	59.92	50.44	65.92	45.87

TABLE II: Testing $NRMSE \times 100\%$ $20\ \mu m$.

Type	A	B	C	D	E
$R^2esNet10$	35.71	48.16	47.64	43.11	29.31
ec- $R^2esNet10$	18.53	30.69	28.05	28.13	26.35
$R^2esNet18$	34.60	47.74	48.04	43.13	26.20
ec- $R^2esNet18$	14.51	33.46	27.13	30.16	26.47
$R^2esNet34$	37.02	46.48	50.81	46.81	25.11
ec- $R^2esNet34$	19.94	28.39	29.45	30.86	22.62
DenseNet	35.61	52.77	38.79	58.89	46.57
ec-DenseNet	15.72	41.74	25.32	45.04	32.47
MobileNetV2	36.68	51.76	38.11	57.30	41.27
ec-MobileNet	17.78	39.03	27.02	43.01	32.88
VGG	39.37	36.62	46.64	40.83	39.55
ec-VGG	24.84	32.63	35.00	31.83	33.33

Inspection times for all 6 PCBs are shown in Table III. We observe that for the most shallow models $R^2esNet10$ and ec- $R^2esNet10$ it takes less than a minute for the inspection of a part, which is a drastic reduction compared to the 20-30 minutes needed in [3] only for the scanning module to operate as shown in Table IV. It is also noted that we have not optimized our implementation for the jetson so there is further room for improvement in terms of execution time

TABLE III: Part inspection times in seconds.

	PCB 1	PCB 2	PCB 3	PCB 4	PCB 5	PCB 6
$R^2esNet10$	45.04	44.38	44.45	44.51	44.48	44.68
ec- $R^2esNet10$	55.60	55.40	55.58	55.41	55.24	55.32
$R^2esNet18$	55.57	54.17	54.21	55.22	54.23	54.39
ec- $R^2esNet18$	64.03	63.58	63.75	63.64	63.73	63.60
$R^2esNet34$	75.41	72.96	72.26	71.46	71.93	72.28
ec- $R^2esNet34$	80.63	81.28	80.81	80.82	81.07	81.09
DenseNet	51.75	51.94	51.44	51.47	50.90	50.77
ec-DenseNet	61.21	60.28	60.35	60.07	59.36	59.16
MobileNetV2	63.63	63.49	63.30	63.38	63.28	63.08
ec-MobileNetV2	90.23	89.33	88.53	88.20	88.26	88.09
VGG	110.54	110.26	11.60	111.98	111.61	111.83
ec-VGG	188.44	190.70	188.29	190.51	190.85	190.37

Testing set predictions for all the developed models are shown in Fig. 14. We observe that the predictions follow the increasing ground truth trend and thus offer insight into the amount of the dispensed glue. Without error correction to regularize the outputs, the predicted volume is usually underestimated, which is attributable to the bias existent in the training samples. On the other hand, after regularization, predictions accurately follow the mean. Furthermore, we notice that the

(a) Type A validation loss (b) Type B validation loss (c) Type C validation loss (d) Type D validation loss (e) Type E validation loss

Fig. 13: Average cross-validation loss of the three trained models for all glue types.

Fig. 14: Testing set predictions for the trained models. On the top row predictions without the use of error-correction are shown, whereas on the bottom the predictions are regularized.

TABLE IV: Scanning and inspection time comparison between [3] and our method.

Model	Scanning time	Inference time	Total time
RNet, 20 μ m	2620	470	3090
RNet, 50 μ m	1181	470	1651
ec-R ² esNet10	≈ 0.17	55.42	55.59
ec-R ² esNet18	≈ 0.17	63.72	63.89
ec-R ² esNet34	≈ 0.17	80.94	81.11
ec-DenseNet	≈ 0.17	60.07	60.24
ec-Mobilenet	≈ 0.17	88.77	88.94
ec-VGG	≈ 0.17	189.86	190.03

performance of the models is directly related to the variance of label noise. Specifically, the MSE is lowest for types A and E, which are the least affected by noise, whereas it is maximal for types B and D.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article we propose a methodology to replace expensive laboratory sensors with in situ ones, and demonstrate its potential by applying it for the development of a PCB inspection system that only relies on the use of an industrial camera and a Jetson unit. The developed system makes use of our R²esNet architecture to perform glue volume regression along with an error-correction network to cope with label noise. Moreover, a segmentation and detection system that significantly simplifies the data acquisition process is developed. An important contribution of this work is the ability of R²esNet to regress a 3D geometric quantity from 2D data.

The effectiveness of our system is demonstrated by the various experiments performed. Despite the challenging nature of the problem addressed, we obtain satisfactory results. Specifically, predictions are accurate enough to facilitate the quality inspection process and hence reduce inspection time, which is a crucial factor towards the optimization of the production process. Another interesting finding is the performance degradation observed for deeper architectures, even though residual networks are specifically build to address this issue.

To further benchmark and evaluate the limitations of the proposed methodology, a potential extension is its deployment in other industrial use cases, where we can explore how well it can generalize in terms of domain adaptation and inferring values outside the nominal ones used during training. Another interesting extension that can further improve the inspection process is the deployment of the proposed system on Augmented Reality (AR) gear.

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